

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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LANGUAGE FEATURES OF ELECTRONIC MASS MEDIA.

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Abstract. Television emerges as an audiovisual medium of mass communication that combines the sound we hear and the image we see. According to TV language researcher O.V. Aleksandrova, telecommunication is, first of all, mass communication. It is an exchange of information in which millions of people from different groups and strata receive and use information. Television discourse is a complex system that combines different parameters, the specifics of the language, the specificity of styles and themes, the diversity of genres.

Key words: Audiovisual, communication, extralinguistic features, communicators.

ELEKTRON OAVLARNING TIL XUSUSIYATLARI.

Annotatsiya. Televideniya biz eshitadigan tovush va biz ko'rgan tasvirni o'zida mujassamlashtirgan audiovizual ommaviy aloqa vositasi sifatida maydonga chiqadi. Televizion til tadqiqotchisi O.V.ning fikricha. Aleksandrovaning ta'kidlashicha, telekommunikatsiya - bu birinchi navbatda ommaviy aloqa. Bu turli guruhlar va qatlamlarga mansub millionlab odamlar axborotni oladigan va foydalanadigan axborot almashinuvidir. Televizion nutq turli parametrlarni, tilning o'ziga xosligini, uslub va mavzularning o'ziga xosligini, janr xilma-xilligini o'zida mujassam etgan murakkab tizimdir.

Kalit so'zlar: audiovizual, aloqa, ekstralingvistik xususiyatlar, kommunikatorlar.

ЯЗЫКОВЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ЭЛЕКТРОННЫХ СМИ.

Аннотация. Телевидение выступает как аудиовизуальное средство массовой коммуникации, сочетающее в себе звук, который мы слышим, и изображение, которое мы видим. По мнению исследователя телевизионного языка О.В. Александрова, телекоммуникации – это прежде всего массовые коммуникации. Это обмен информацией, при котором миллионы людей из разных групп и слоев получают и используют информацию. Телевизионный

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Том 2, Выпуск 5, 31 Май

дискурс представляет собой сложную систему, сочетающую в себе разные параметры, специфику языка, специфику стилей и тем, многообразие жанров.

Ключевые слова: Аудиовизуальное, коммуникация, экстралингвистические особенности, коммуникаторы.

Introduction. Today, the language of audiovisual means attracts the attention of many linguists. In the process of studying the specifics of audiovisual media, television theorists focused on the possibilities of television and the characteristics of the genres of television journalism. They approached the problems of teletext from the point of view of traditional practical stylistics, lexical and syntactic stylistics of teletext. S. V. Svetana studied telegraph speech in her monograph “Television Speech: Functions and Structure” and introduced the concept of “television speech” as a scientific term. After analyzing television texts, the author conducted an experiment to determine the characteristics of television speech and came to the following conclusions. Television language researcher S.V. According to Svetana, television historians and theorists felt the magical power of the image in the early stages of creating the television genre. Later, the audio-visual nature of television was discussed, but no emphasis was placed on the concept of ‘sound’. Clearly, television channels transmit not only sound, noisy images, music, but also live human voice - speech. It is therefore advisable to consider the “image-sound-speech” trinity when studying television. Considering television in such a trinity, on the one hand, allows us to consider the most important features of television as one of the modern media, and on the other hand, proves that television provides rich material for observing live speech processes.

As we can see, the image-voice-speech trio is also a complex system, each element of which is aimed at ensuring the most effective communication between the journalist and the audience. Our task is to analyze the role of speech in this trio and to show which style is most important for successful communication. In this case, we study the prosodic features of the speech of TV presenters in terms of the specific functions of television speech, the format of the TV channel, the genre of the program, the audiovisuality.

We can see the influence of extralinguistic factors on the structure of television speech. Extralinguistic factors also determine the non-linguistic constitution that creates the conditions for the realization of telepathy.

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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Том 2, Выпуск 5, 31 Май

In this case, extralinguistic features are formed on the basis of a number of conditions studied by neighboring, closely related disciplines, such as logic and psychology. When we study the process of real speech communication, we consider not only the process of speech formation that psychologists focus on, but also the characteristics of the speaker (listener) and the writer (reader) who are the carrier and receiver. Information in each specific speech act. It is known that television channels transmit not only sound or noisy images, music, but also a live human voice - speech.

The advantage of television over other media is that it combines the image of the speaker and the image of the speaker. Viewers will be addressed live on television. It appears suddenly and represents a mature thought. It is the word of a speaker, orator, commentator, or sage.

The study of teletology in general, and in particular its prozodic components, should be based on the following. It is important for telecommunications not only that language forms express ideas in speech, but also that speech is evaluated, that personal and social characteristics of communicators, their knowledge of science, the field of communication, and the social situation are preserved. It can be said that the social and personal characteristics of communicators (addressee and addressee), the direct conditions of their communication, require a certain type of speech and therefore determine the choice of the prozodic standard. The analysis of speech on television should take into account the “set of conditions that currently affect the individual”.

Conclusion. Radio and television should convey to the people not only advanced ideas and knowledge, but also a high language culture. The program should include the relevance of the topic of the broadcast, the requirements for the clarity of the form, as well as the requirements for the broadcast speech, in particular, the literature on the speech, the accuracy and uniformity of pronunciation. In our opinion, the air should be clear and beautiful. Such speech can be a norm of speech. For television practitioners and theorists, the question arises: what is the advantage of television - word or image? anavi. In our opinion, there is no clear answer to this question, as both of them have not been studied in depth.

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МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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SJIF 2024 = 5.444

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МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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